

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MOGOLLON****FIRST NAME: NESTOR****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied X US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author X did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 1%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List 5 to 7 key concepts with page numbers in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay writing (EUCLID 2023, 6-14)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2023, 33-39)
3. Some rules of thumb for writing a paper (EUCLID 2023, 12-14)
4. Style guide (EUCLID 2023, 40 - 58)
5. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2023, 51-55)

HOW TO WRITE A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

After reading the ACA-401/ACA 401-D course pack revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma, as well as watching the tutorial videos of the course presented by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck, I have realized that writing a good academic paper requires not only knowing grammar rules and the basics of writing but also preparation, dedication, and time for editing in order to have a clear and coherent paper that can convey your arguments to the readers. In addition, we have to comply with citation rules to give credit to the works of the authors we are using to support our arguments. In other words, we must avoid plagiarism, which is a severe fault in academic writing.

It is important to note that to write a good response paper, we must carefully review the punctuation, especially comma use, spelling, style, and tone of our writing. Furthermore, we need to check the English version we are using because, although both American and British versions are acceptable, we cannot combine them in the paper. We need to decide which version to use right at the beginning. Consistency is the key here.

If we want to be successful in our Ph.D. studies, academic writing is one of the foundation blocks to communicate in the academic world.

In this response paper, I will discuss the five major topics that I learned to be critical for writing a good essay paper according to the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack for the first period and the basic tutorial videos. These include essay writing, plagiarism, rules of thumb for writing a good paper, a style guide, and American vs. British English.

2) HOW TO WRITE A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

Academic writing is a particular kind of writing whose style can be recognized. It includes essays, research papers, reports, articles, case studies, surveys, dissertations, theses, and examination papers.

Academic writing is mainly formal, impersonal, and objective. In addition, specific types of academic writing may have other distinctive features. In addition, Academic writing is more than just another way to write; it is literally a different culture with its own language (Singh and Lukkarila 2017, 4).

Although academic writing has some similarities, it is important to highlight that different disciplines have different purposes, tones, structures, styles, audiences, and word choices specific to that field.

The main purpose of academic essays is to provide answer(s) to hypotheses and communicate ideas based on evidence (EUCLID 2023, 7).

Before writing an academic essay, it is important to understand the task and the questions to be addressed and have an initial plan to help us organize our research.

Writing an academic paper includes different stages that must be considered carefully to produce the final product. First, the topic, subject, or question should be clearly understood. Then, it is important to make notes of any knowledge or experience we may have about the subject. After this, we can search for books, journals, articles, etc., and keep adding new ones while looking for the recommended reading list or bibliography.

When the books have been identified, it is time to read those books, journals, and articles with a purpose and always keep the topic or question of the essay clearly in mind in order to find sound evidence to support your argument (EUCLID 2023, 9). Furthermore, notes should be taken from the reading of the information sources. In addition, we need to keep a record of all the sources to create a list of references that can be organized at the end of the essay. Any quotations should be accurately acknowledged using the same standard and format throughout the paper (EUCLID 2023, 11).

Then, we should organize the content of the essay and write our first draft. The course pack suggests an essay structure: the introduction, the main body, and the conclusion. It is essential that the first draft be written in a formal or academic style, avoiding colloquial expressions and personal references. When the draft is completed, we need to read it critically, especially looking at its language, organization, clearness, conciseness, and comprehensiveness.

Afterward, the essay should be carefully edited in particular to check the overall structure of the essay; ensure paragraphs relate to the argument and are arranged in a logical sequence; revise the grammar of sentences and check the punctuation and spelling. (EUCLID 2023, 12). The final step is to submit the essay, taking into consideration the guidelines of the course.

3) PLAGIARISM

“Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2023, 34). Some examples of plagiarism are copying and pasting from the Internet and not giving credit to the author, having someone write a paper for you, and then putting your name on it. (EUCLID 2023, 34).

There are several reasons why plagiarism should be avoided. We need to learn how to speak our minds and not merely repeat the words of others; we need to learn to assess critically the work of others to draw our own conclusions and develop our own voice. We should avoid plagiarism because it will prevent us from producing the highest quality work. However, this means that we can use the work of others in our own work; on the contrary, it is critical that we use and discuss the material written by others to support our own arguments in our discipline but with due acknowledgment and proper referencing. In other words, we need to credit the authors of the ideas and data we cite. This practice will not only recognize their work but also strengthen our argument and give the readers the opportunity to check your references and check how valid your interpretations are.

I learned from the course pack that plagiarism is not only wrong and unethical, but it is also unfair to take another author’s work and not give them the corresponding credit. Furthermore, it is also considered a serious academic offense, shows poor scholarship, and means we have failed to complete the learning process. As a result, I am very clear now that I should avoid plagiarism in all my work.

The question is how to avoid plagiarism. According to EUCLID (2023, 34-39), the solution is properly citing the author and source that has provided the information. This includes data, graphs, words, paraphrases, and so on.

Finally, we need to remember that as a principle of honesty, we should acknowledge the work of other researchers and not pass it as our own work.

4) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPERS

Writing a good paper requires keeping in mind some rules that will make the document coherent, clear, and right to the point.

I noticed that is very important to state the main thesis of your paper at the beginning as well as focus the discussion of your topic without distracting the reader with

other unrelated ideas. In other words, direct your readers right to the point you want them to understand.

It is very important also that your paper is written clearly, using short sentences, not using long paragraphs and good transitions. Moreover, try to use simple language to better convey your ideas to the readers.

I learned from the course material that an essay should be written, avoiding boring or clumsy language. Furthermore, it is important to use some stylistic variety as well as not repeating the same words, and active voice is preferred instead of passive constructions.

One important aspect of writing a paper is to provide support for the argument you are presenting. This can be done either by noting relevant passages or using quotations. Generally, a passage should be quoted only if it plays an important role in the paper (EUCLID 2023, 13). However, I will always remember not to submit a paper with many quotations.

Another important rule is that when we make a criticism, we need to be respectful because authors have spent lots of time and reflection writing their views and even have asked for feedback from other people and incorporated responses to any objections they received into their final documents (EUCLID 2023, 14). If we need to criticize an author in our writing, first, by default, we could assume that we have misinterpreted their ideas and ask ourselves how the author would respond to our criticism.

Finally, the last but not least rule is to refrain from plagiarizing. Plagiarism is unacceptable in any academic writing. I noted from the course that there are two types of plagiarism: using a source's words without quotation marks and taking ideas from a source without acknowledging it. Both types of plagiarism are sanctioned (EUCLID 2023, 14).

In summary, I learned that applying these rules of thumb will help me prepare better papers for this course and all my Ph.D. studies at EUCLID. Also, the more I practice them, the more I will master them.

5) STYLE GUIDE

A style guide is a means of documenting your one's approach as a writer to maintain a certain writing style consistent with (EUCLID 2023, 41). I learned that writing style guides are particularly important in technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and copywriting because most of the time several writers are working together and need to ensure that the writing style is consistent. In addition, style guides ensure that the final piece carries the publication style and not the personal style of the writer.

In contrast with the use of punctuation and correct grammar that is well-established and clear, there is only one authoritative source on style for written English. For this reason, there is and will always be a certain debate on style elements because style goes beyond just the correct usage of punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary (EUCLID 2023, 41).

EUCLID recommends using the Chicago Rules (Turabian) but also accepts other internationally recognized Rules. Although EUCLID recommends using American English, both American and British versions are accepted as long as they are not used interchangeably. I must admit that this was the first time I heard about Turabian, and I am excited to learn it. I think that by using it regularly, I will be able to master it. In addition, the BBC News style guide included in the reading material seems interesting to review.

6) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

The difference between American English and British English is not solely in the pronunciation of words or spelling differences in words such as ‘theatre,’ ‘Centre,’ ‘mum,’ and so on. However, in regard to “educated or “scientific English,” they are more similar than different (EUCLID 2023, 25).

Although both American English and British English can be used to write academic papers in EUCLID, it is considered a mistake to combine them throughout the paper unless it is a quote that needs to be kept in the original language. It is very useful that the EUCLID template provides the option to choose which English version to use right at the beginning.

I noticed that, especially for academic writing, American English and British English have important differences that I need to master when using one or the other. An example of this is the differences in punctuation and dates, the use of periods, commas, and quotation marks, and punctuation with business vs social letters (EUCLID 2023 31-32).

7) CONCLUSION

After reading the course pack for this course, I realized that to write a good academic essay, I will need to master several writing rules, writing conventions, principles, writing styles, and so on. In the beginning, it could be seen as an overwhelming task to learn so many rules and at the same time try to write a paper, but I think it will be a matter of practice and using them consistently to produce a good academic paper. This is what I will commit myself to do.

The material of the course pack as well as the videos are very comprehensive and have useful guidance and tips on how to prepare, organize, and write a good academic paper, which is a critical skill to pursue my Ph.D. studies at Euclid University.

Finally, I am confident that with practice, dedication, and the great material of this course, I will master the art of writing academic papers and have the basic skills to continue writing in the following course and especially to prepare my dissertation.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1*. Fourth Edition Bangui: Euclid University.

Singh, Anneliese, and Lauren Lukkarila. 2017. "Defining Academic Writing." In: *Successful Academic Writing: A Complete Guide for Social and Behavioral Scientists*. The Guildford Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.